

ISSN 2181-9505
Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9505

Philosophy and Life

FALSAFA VA HAYOT • ФИЛОСОФИЯ И ЖИЗНЬ

2024 № 2 (25)

ISSN 2181-9505
Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9505

Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy Universiteti
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi
Imom Buxoriy xalqaro ilmiy-tadqiqot markazi
O'zbekiston falsafa jamiyati

Национальный Университет Узбекистана имени Мирзо Улугбека
Международный научно-исследовательский центр Имам Бухари
при Кабинете Министров Республики Узбекистан
Философское общество Узбекистана

The National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek
Imam Bukhari International Research Center under the Cabinet of Ministers
of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Philosophical Society of Uzbekistan

**FALSAFA VA HAYOT
XALQARO JURNAL**

**ФИЛОСОФИЯ И ЖИЗНЬ
МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ**

**PHILOSOPHY AND LIFE
INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL**

2024 № 2 (25)

Jurnal bir yilda 4 marta nashr qilinadi.
Журнал выходит 4 раза в год.
The journal is published 4 times in a year.

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WORLD CULTURE AND RELIGIOUS TRADITIONS**

UDK: 316.7.8:001.8

 10.5281/zenodo.12611796

Кожевников Николай Николаевич

профессор кафедры философии

Северо-Восточный Федеральный Университет, Якутск, Россия

E-mail: nnkozhev@mail.ru

Данилова Вера Софроновна

профессор кафедры философии

Северо-Восточный Федеральный Университет, Якутск, Россия

E-mail: nikkozkh@gmail.com

(Якутск, Россия)

**ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ АВТОБИОГРАФИИ ФЕНОМЕНОЛОГИЧЕСКИМ
И ГЕРМЕНЕВТИЧЕСКИМ МЕТОДАМИ**

Аннотация. Существует три типа биографии: формальная биография, внутренняя фундаментальная автобиография и внешняя фундаментальная автобиография. Формальная биография сводит описание жизни к схемам, используемым в служебных, карьерных и других подобных целях. Фундаментальная биография имеет ориентацию на определенный предел, который будет называться направлением: идентификация, общение и ритмы мировой гармонии соответственно. Идентификацию изучаемой жизни можно охарактеризовать как переход от явления к явлению, общение - как переход от горизонта к горизонту, а ритмизацию - как очищение основного (опорного) ритма, характеризующего саму жизнь и систему, обеспечивающую ее существование. В результате образуется ячейка, состоящая из трех фундаментальных пределов динамических равновесий, на которых и должна основываться «истинная» автобиография. Взаимодействуя с пределами динамических равновесий, «вещи есть существование» жизни превращаются в бытие жизни. Взаимодействие с пределами обеспечивает трансформацию «вещи есть существование» в его квазиравновесное описание или текст «вещи есть существование» - бытие. Непосредственно индивиду дано бытие «вещей есть существование» индивидуума. Именно оно доступно его восприятию, ведь мы всегда воспринимаем не саму «вещь есть существование», а ее текст.

Ключевые слова: идентификация, общение, ритм, гармония, вещи есть существование, динамическое равновесие.

FENOMENOLOGIK VA GERMENEVTIK METODLAR ORQALI AVTOBIOGRAFIYALARNI TADQIQ ETISH

Annotatsiya. Biografiyalarning uch turi mavjud: formal biografiya, ichki fundamental avtobiografiya va tashqi fundamental avtobiografiya. Formal biografiyada hayot turli xizmat, karyer yoki shunga oʻxshash sxemalarga moslanadi. Fundamental biografiya muayyan chegaraga qadar yoʻnalgan boʻlib, ularni yoʻnalishlar bor. Ularni mos ravishda identifikatsiya, muloqot va dunyoviy uygʻunlik ritmlari deb atash mumkin. Oʻrganilayotgan hayot identifikatsiyasi deganda hodisadan-hodisaga oʻtishni tushunish mumkin. Muloqot esa ufqdan-ufqqa oʻtish, ritmlashtirishni esa hayotning oʻzini va uning mavjudligini taʼminlovchi asosiy (tayanch) ritmni tozalash deb tushunish mumkin. Buning natijasida dinamik muvozanatning uch fundamental chagaralaridan tashkil topuvchi katak hosil boʻladi va avtobiografiya ham aynan shunga asoslanishi kerak. Dinamik muvozanat chegaralari bilan oʻzaro aloqaga kirishar ekan hayotning “narsalar - mavjudlikdir” jihati hayot mavjudligiga aylanadi. Chegaralar bilan aloqaga kirishish “narsalar - mavjudlikdir”ni uning kvazi-muvozanatdagi tafsilotiga, yoki “narsalar - mavjudlikdir” ning matniga – hayotga aylanadi. Aynan shu narsa idrok uchun ochiq, chunki biz “narsalar - mavjudlikdir”ning oʻzini emas, uning matnini idrok etamiz.

Kalit soʻzlar: identifikatsiya, muloqot, ritm, uygʻunlik, narsalar – mavjudlikdir, dinamik muvozanat.

THE STUDY OF «AUTOBIOGRAPHY» BY METHODS OF PHENOMENOLOGY AND HERMENEUTICS

Annotation. There are three types of biography: a formal biography, internal fundamental autobiography and external fundamental autobiography. Formal biography reduces the description of life to the schemes used for official, career and other similar purposes. The fundamental biography have the orientation to a specific limit will be called a direction: identification, communication and to the rhythms of world harmony, respectively. The identification of life under study can be characterized as a transition from a phenomenon to a phenomenon, communication as a transition from horizon to a horizon and rhythmization as clearing of the fundamental (supporting) rhythm that characterizes life itself and the system that ensures its existence. As a result, a cell is formed consisting of three fundamental limits of dynamic equilibria, on which the “true” autobiography should be based. Interacting with the limits of dynamic equilibria, the “things are existence” of life turns into the being of life. The interaction with the limits provides the transformation of the “things are existence” to its quasi-equilibrium description or text of the “things are existence” - being. Directly to the individual is given the being of “things are existence” to the individual. It is precisely it that is accessible to its perception, because we always perceive not the very “things are existence”, but its text.

Keywords: identification, communication, rhythm, harmony, things are existence, dynamic equilibria.

INTRODUCTION

Biography is a key element to clarify the concepts of "individual", "personality", "Ego". There are three types of it: a formal biography and fundamental autobiography (internal and external), which are philosophical projections of life.

Formal biography reduces the description of life to the schemes used for official, career and other similar purposes. This biography may include major life milestones related to birth, upbringing, education, etc. The basis of such a biography is the "logos", which can be supplemented with some bright strokes. In its final form, it is already formed in the after-death, and bright strokes appear in it thanks to the memories of friends, relatives, published letters, etc. The first of the fundamental autobiographies (internal) is associated with the identification of the "things are existence" of his "Ego", the second (external) - with the formation of being as the text of the "things are existence" intended to interact with other things of the world.

The fundamental biography is due to the ineradicable need of the individual to find his essence and ensure its interaction with the environment. A fundamental biography is necessary when summing up the vital results, extracting from them certain lessons, orienting the remaining life to the most important goals.

It is possible to draw analogies between the biographies and the interpretation of I. Kant and A. Bergson of various religions. Kant divided religions into statutory and moral [Kant I., 1966]. Bergson considered two types of religion and morality: static and dynamic [Bergson A., 2010]. The formal and fundamental (internal and external) biographies discussed above can also be considered as static and dynamic, but they can complement each other in a natural way. To identify the mechanisms of this process, a comprehensive philosophical analysis of the features of the formation of the autobiography as a whole is necessary.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fundamental inner autobiography is connected with revealing the essence of one's "Ego". It is an interpretation of "life" and takes part in its formation. If the concrete life is reduced to a set of real circumstances, then they somehow interact with the inner world of the individual. Depending on the perception of these inner worlds, the behavior of different people under the same external conditions is very different from each other.

For the same life, there can be several variants of the fundamental autobiography. In many works of classical and post-classical literature, autobiographical motives play a main role, although they can be deliberately distorted, which makes it possible to examine a person from various sides, to make the necessary accents, to explore key life events from different angles. These motives may be random, inappropriate to the inner essence of the individual, tend to form instead of the essence of different roles and personality simulacra. Sometimes, in order to reveal the essence of a person, it is necessary to consider it

in a negative light, as for example F.M. Dostoevsky does [Dostoevsky F.M., 2023].

Is it possible to classify autobiographies by their quality, authenticity? Is it possible to identify the "true" autobiography, which will contribute to self-organization and harmonization of the personality and its essence? If these processes are based on the limits of dynamic equilibria: identification, communication, rhythmization and then such a "true" autobiography seems possible. The essence of the personality is one, but its representations, conditioned by the circumstances of life, can be quite a lot and even more so representations of the essence in being. If an individual intends to become a person, then he needs to find both his essence and the mechanisms that ensure the stability of its existence.

The orientation to a specific limit will be called a direction: identification, communication and to the rhythms of world harmony, respectively. The identification of life under study can be characterized as a transition from a phenomenon to a phenomenon, communication as a transition from horizon to a horizon and rhythmization as clearing of the fundamental (supporting) rhythm that characterizes life itself and the system that ensures its existence. As a result, a cell is formed consisting of three fundamental limits of dynamic equilibria, on which the "true" autobiography should be based [Kozhevnikov N., 2005, p. 46].

Life is an open thing (system) and participates in the processes of self-organization, which are based on the aforementioned limits of dynamic equilibria. The desire to limit of the identification step by step reveals its existence. Orientation to the limit of communication ensures the sustainability of the existence of the things is existence of this thing. Rhythmization ensures the finding of the most stable rhythms for: 1) the things is existence and 2) the system ensuring its existence [Kozhevnikov N., 2013, p. 365].

Identification begins with the identification of the brightest strokes (emotional, intellectual) characterizing the life of an individual, from which, over time, as a result of self-organization, only those remain that define the fundamental frame of the personality. This self-selection of stable dynamic equilibria is ensured by continuous interaction with all three limits noted above. The formation of stable things and their finding of their existence can only be based on the limit equilibria of the coordinate system, which, in addition to identifying the concrete thing, provides it with a stable existence and connection with the fundamental rhythms of the world.

Striving for the limit of identification defines life as the search for oneself, which can only be achieved because of free self-organization "... a person is free, a person is freedom ... a person is condemned to be free. Condemned because he did not create himself; and yet free, because once thrown into the world is responsible for everything that it does" [Sartre J., 1990, p. 327]. The environment always hampers realizing the ideal of free formation of oneself, but the desire for such an ideal is a worthy program of life and it is inherent in man himself. Autobiographical identification is an extremely difficult process that requires overcoming continuous daily difficulties.

The autobiographical limit of communication determines the desire to create an optimal and stable system from one's "Ego". Sifting out everything that interferes with its integrity, optimality is also a worthy life program. In the second half of life, Heidegger's "Being to death" can be considered the main mechanism here [Heidegger M., 2003, p. 287]. This program counts life from the day of death, which no one among the living knows, but reliance on which allows someone to feel a resource that has been released to a person. At the same time, it is possible to rely in this period of the life only on the fundamental framework of the personality, since all other models of life become unnecessary, redundant and destructive.

Orientation to autobiographical rhythms of life is the desire to find the rhythms of the person, first of all, the basic reference rhythm, which should be associated with the fundamental rhythms of the world. Sustainable and optimal rhythms and rhythm cascades associated with world harmony draw the whole world down and prevail over the destructive tendencies taking place in it. Man is involved in more than a hundred circadian rhythms, which are determined by the rotation of the Earth, the Sun, cyclic processes in the Galaxy, Metagalaxy, etc. If the processes within human existence do not correspond to the rhythms of world harmony, then such a life will be unstable and will end up most likely in a negative way.

Thus, the "true" autobiography is the interaction of life with the limits of dynamic equilibria, the "refraction" of it through them. It is a monitoring of life, taking into account its past and future. Compared to life, autobiographies are easier to have a permanent connection with the above described limits, to "cling" to them. Based on the experience of the past and this "hooking", the autobiography can direct life to inner freedom, optimal communication with the outside world and its fundamental rhythms.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Autobiography as a text of life. The fundamental external autobiography is connected with the transformation of the essence of life into a text that should be unique, giving the most complete picture of a person and his epoch. In other words, it must be implemented through the dynamic equilibrium limits described above. This text does not have to be highly artistic, as long as it is yours.

The set of steps (calibration intervals) in which a person moves along the path of self-organization — from the phenomenon, as an element of identification of a dynamic equilibrium cell to the next phenomenon [Svasyan K.A., 2010], will be a set of certain signs. The calibration interval is their core and is determined for each specific direction by two other limits. That is, if a step is made in the direction of the identification limit, it should contribute to the optimality and stability of the emerging communication system and the approximation of the reference rhythms of this object to the fundamental rhythms of world harmony. A cell composed of the above described limits will be stable only when the phenomenon moves exactly to such a calibration interval.

The same can be said about the steps in the direction of the limits of communication and rhythmization, which also form a system of signs based on their corresponding calibration intervals. That is, the interaction of all three limits will provide the calibration of movements in any of the above directions. A set of texts in all three directions will give the final text describing a particular life.

Interacting with the limits of dynamic equilibria, the “things are existence” of life turns into the being of life. The interaction with the limits provides the transformation of the “things are existence” that forms instead of the “things are existence” its quasi-equilibrium description or text of the “things are existence” - being. Directly to the individual is given the being of “things are existence” to the individual. It is precisely it that is accessible to its perception, because we always perceive not the very “things are existence”, but its text. For example, the Sun as a thermonuclear reactor can cause only horror, but transformed by earth shells, distance, it seems to us very pleasant, a person likes to interact with it (not with the Sun as a reactor, but with its text). The same is the case with all other phenomena of the non-living and living world, spheres of social and humanitarian. Other people also interact not with the person, but with his text, often with what he himself represents - with his autobiography. First, they do not know his “things are existence”, which can be very unpleasant and even scary, and secondly, the individual himself seeks to appear before other people in a certain light, usually embellishing himself. In addition, these texts (autobiographies) can only ensure the stability of a specific human life (project of life) when they are associated with all three limits of dynamic equilibria in the past, present and future.

Mechanisms of autobiography formation. A person lives in the semiosphere, interacting with hundreds of different languages, most of which in one-way or another affect his life and its description options. Interaction with the semiosphere depends on the epoch, ethnic characteristics, mentality and much more. However, the text of being focused on clarifying things is the most important thing in the external fundamental autobiography.

Based on the above, we will highlight three mechanisms for the interaction of fundamental autobiography with life. 1. Through constant listening to oneself. 2. Through the use of book and visual texts that identify sign systems that activate special “points”, “areas”, “strings” of the mind, soul, and facilitate their memorization. 3. Dedication of life to its main business. As a result, the autobiography can be represented as interrelated elements of the hermeneutic triangle: “Ego” - the texts of my “Ego” – the main matter of life. All these mechanisms complement each other, that is, an autobiography is formed simultaneously with life.

The first of these approaches is associated with internal texts aimed at identifying its essence. The need to systematically recall one’s life is the essential quality of a person. The deepest of these memories are with the sequential movement of the gaze back through the bright and unique structures of the life of the individual. The basis of such a view becomes “eidos” [Motroshilova N.V.,

2003], which presupposes a figurative seizure of life situations supplemented by their intellectual intuition and understanding [Betty E., 2011].

The second of these approaches (method) is related to book texts. The process of reading gradually teaches the reader to listen to the text, contributes to the formation of the text, according to its readers' standards. Gradually, this process extends to the formation of his autobiography, which becomes the monitoring of life. He constantly sounds in the individual, like a certain melody and from a certain stage begins to direct his life. From this moment in life, a person begins to read only "his" books, deal with certain people or reduce these contacts altogether to an acceptable social minimum. All this adjusts the individual to the limiting dynamic equilibria. All texts and memories are subordinate to the goals of forming an autobiography oriented to the "things are essence" [Husserl E., 1991].

In the third mechanism, an autobiography aimed at the main business of life helps to cleanse it of everything superfluous. Autobiography at the same time begins to rely only on what contributed to the formation of this vital rod. This mechanism quickly leads the individual to the limiting dynamic equilibria.

The foregoing is closely related to Heidegger's hermeneutic approach [Heidegger M., 2008] which distinguishes two groups of meanings: "world" and "earth". In our case, there is a directly observable "world" and all the limiting dynamic equilibria ensuring its stable existence, which should be denoted as "earth." Expanding the interpretation of the above approach by G. Gadamer, it can be argued that between the "world" and the "earth" there is a constant complementary rivalry [Gadamer G., 1991] reminiscent of the relationship between the fundamental categories of ancient Chinese philosophy "yang" and "yin" [Philosophy of social and human sciences, 2008]. The "world" in its interaction with the "earth" constantly creates new elements and cells of the coordinate system, in relation to which it steadily and optimally develops. However, he exposes them to a very tough selection, discarding everything unnecessary at a particular stage of his development and leaving only what is necessary for the next specific step. The "earth" rests on all possible limiting dynamic equilibria of the "world", on the whole harmony of the universal coordinate system, providing the concrete structures of the world with stability.

What is contained in the "earth" is undoubtedly more in volume and value than what is contained in the "world." The main task of an individual and of humanity as a whole is to ensure the existence of a coordinate system of the world based on dynamic equilibria. Such provision is the main priority activity of the world, nature, and in the future will become the main occupation of humanity [Lyotard J. F., 2001].

CONCLUSION

An important aspect of the mutual monitoring of "world" and "earth" is the separation of the truth of life from lies. There can be no secrets in the world, everything that is hidden in it will be revealed eventually. However, the "earth" is the natural place of all secrets is the world's coordinate system based on

deterministic chaos. All notions and concepts that have ontological “roots” in this coordinate system, for example “vacuum”, “spirituality” are extremely complex things. In order to focus on the issues of exploring the world around us and move away from the secrets of the coordinate system, it is necessary to perceive the notions under study as the limit attractors.

Any secret hides any problem that seeks to identify as a result of self-organizing processes taking place in the world. Usually this is not completely possible, but the choice of the direction of intentionality and clarification of the stages of identification already clarify a lot ones. A many of research teams are working on every serious problem, individual results of their work fall into the global information field, playing the role of catalysts and significantly speed up the identification process. Communication is currently developing new mechanisms and approaches focused on the formation of optimal and sustainable systems in all fields of knowledge. From a certain stage of development, when information became a determining factor for the development of humanity, the activity of these processes increased dramatically. The fifth and sixth information revolutions, caused by the emergence of computer and planetary networks (cultural, scientific) ensured a deeper and wider self-development and self-deepening of the corresponding processes. As the secret becomes obscure, artificial methods of its preservation appear more and more difficult. These include misinformation and intimidation of its carriers, who, if this secret is discovered, will face severe punishment. However, in spite of everything, the secrets of the "world" are temporary; they can be preserved only in the "earth".

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**FALSAFA VA HAYOT//
ФИЛОСОФИЯ И ЖИЗНЬ//
PHILOSOPHY AND LIFE**

Tahririyat manzili	Адрес редакции	Editors Address
100085, O‘zbekiston Toshkent, Sergeli tumani, Mehrigiyo ko‘chasi -6	100085, Узбекистан, Ташкент Сергелинский район, Улица Мехригиё- 6	100085, Uzbekistan Tashkent Sergeli, Mehrigiyo street-6

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